

Global existence for nonlinear bi-parabolic equation under globally Lipschitz condition

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Abstract

The bi-parabolic equation plays a large role in the theory of heat transfer. Our main goal is to consider the existence of a nonlinear bi-parabolic equation with globally Lipschitz of the source term. With some suitable conditions of the input data, we prove the global unique existence of the mild solution. The main technique in the paper is to use Banach's fixed point theorem in combination with the $L^p - L^q$ estimates. This paper seems to generalize previous results for the bi-parabolic equation in this direction.

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1. Introduction

Let Ω be a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N ($N \geq 1$) with sufficiently smooth boundary $\partial\Omega$. In this paper, we study the initial value problem for following bi-parabolic equation

$$\begin{cases} y_{tt}(x, t) + 2\Delta y_t(x, t) + \Delta^2 y(x, t) = G(y(x, t)), & \text{in } \Omega \times (0, T], \\ y|_{\partial\Omega} = \Delta y|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y(x, 0) = y_0(x), & \text{in } \Omega \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

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where G is the source function, representing the effect of an external force, and y describes the distribution at time t and space x . Some various topics related to this problem are of interest to many mathematicians, for example Lakhdari-Boussetila [1], Besma-Nadjib-Rebbani [2], Tuan-Kirane-Nam-Au [3], Tuan-Caraballo-Thach [4], [12, 9, 5, 6, 8, 7, 10, 11].

In order for the reader to clearly understand the physical meaning of the bi-parabolic equation, we give some illustrative details in the following few lines. The bi-parabolic equation represents heat conduction and has many important applications for thermal processes [13, 14, 15] and it has been used to efficiently describe the special phenomena of dynamic filter fusion process [16, 17, 18]. As described by Fushchich-Galitsyn-Polubinskii[19], the authors have carefully explained that classical quadratic parabolic equations cannot accurately describe heat and mass transfer processes and as such there exist some well-known paradoxes in heat transfer. To overcome some of the above weaknesses, mathematicians have discovered a new parabolic model, which is to replace the second-order operator with the fourth-order operator. That is also the reason, why we have quadratic in terms of t and quadratic in terms of x on the left side of the first equation.

In other words, the equation (1.1) is also a sub-branch of the higher-order PDE equation: it is quadratic in terms of time variables and quadratic in terms of space variables, which attracts many mathematicians to study and interest [20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26].

The present paper uses the main idea from the paper, but contains many other detailed techniques. The principal techniques in our paper is Banach fixed point together with some evaluations of $L^p - L^q$. It can be said that this paper is one of the first results to study the existence of global solutions for bi-parabolic equations in the mild sense.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 deals with some function spaces and embeddings. Section 3 deals with regularized solution for the inverse source problem. The backward problem for linear bi-parabolic equation is investigated in section 4 with observed data in L^p . Section 5 examines the backward problem for nonlinear bi-parabolic equation. The Fourier series truncation method was used for both sections. The main technique of this paper is to use embeddings and Fourier series.

2. Preliminary results

In this section, we introduce the notation and the functional setting which shall be used in our paper. Recall that the spectral problem

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\varphi_n(x) = -\lambda_n\varphi_n(x), & x \in \Omega, \\ \varphi_n(x) = 0, & x \in \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

admits the eigenvalues $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_n \leq \dots$ with $\lambda_n \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. The corresponding eigenfunctions are $\varphi_n \in H_0^1(\Omega)$.

Definition 2.1. [27] (*Hilbert scale space*). We recall the Hilbert scale space, which is given as follows

$$\mathbb{H}^s(\Omega) = \left\{ f \in L^2(\Omega), \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^{2s} \left(\int_{\Omega} f(x)\psi_n(x)dx \right)^2 < \infty \right\},$$

for any $s \geq 0$. It is well-known that $\mathbb{H}^s(\Omega)$ is a Hilbert space corresponding to the norm

$$\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^s(\Omega)} = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^{2s} \left(\int_{\Omega} f(x)\psi_n(x)dx \right)^2 \right)^{1/2}, \quad f \in \mathbb{H}^s(\Omega).$$

3. Global existence of the mild solution

3.1. Representation of source function

Let us give the explicit fomula of the mild solution. First, taking the inner product of both sides of (1.1) with $\varphi_n(x)$, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left(\int_{\Omega} y(x, t) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) + 2\lambda_n \left(\int_{\Omega} y(x, t) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) \\ + \lambda_n^2 \left(\int_{\Omega} y(x, t) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) = \int_{\Omega} F(y(x, t)) \varphi_n(x) dx. \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

It is easy to see that the latter problem has a solution given by

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} y(x, t) \varphi_n(x) dx = e^{-t\lambda_n} (1 + t\lambda_n) \int_{\Omega} u_0(x) \varphi_n(x) dx \\ + \int_0^t (t - r) e^{-(t-r)\lambda_n} \left(\int_{\Omega} F(y(x, r)) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) dr. \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

where we note that $u(x, 0) = u_0(x)$. Let $\mathcal{S}(t)$ is a semigroup generated by the Laplacian $-\Delta$. The representation of $\mathcal{S}(t)f$ as a Fourier series is given by the following obvious formula

$$\mathcal{S}(t)f = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-t\lambda_n} \left(\int_{\Omega} f(x) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) \varphi_n(x), \quad f \in L^2(\Omega). \tag{3.3}$$

Let us provide the operator $\mathcal{Q}(t)$ as follows

$$\mathcal{Q}(t)f = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 + t\lambda_n) \left(\int_{\Omega} f(x) \varphi_n(x) dx \right) \varphi_n(x). \tag{3.4}$$

The mild solution ...

$$y(x, t) = \mathcal{S}(t)\mathcal{Q}(t)u_0 + \int_0^t (t - r)\mathcal{S}(t - r)F(y(x, r))dr. \tag{3.5}$$

Lemma 3.1. *Let p, q satisfy $1 \leq q \leq p$. Then $e^{-t\mathcal{A}}$ is extended to a bounded linear operator from $L^q(\Omega)$ to $L^p(\Omega)$ for each $t > 0$. In addition, the following assertion holds*

$$\|e^{-t\mathcal{A}}f\|_{L^p(\Omega)} \leq Ct^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q}-\frac{1}{p})} \|f\|_{L^q(\Omega)}, \tag{3.6}$$

$$\|\nabla e^{-t\mathcal{A}}f\|_{L^p(\Omega)} \leq Ct^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q}-\frac{1}{p})-\frac{1}{2}} \|f\|_{L^q(\Omega)} \tag{3.7}$$

$$\|e^{-t\mathcal{A}}f\|_{W^{1,p}} \leq Ct^{-\frac{1}{2}} \|f\|_{L^p} \tag{3.8}$$

$$\|\mathcal{A}^\beta e^{-t\mathcal{A}}f\|_{L^p(\Omega)} \leq C(\beta, N, q, p)t^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q}-\frac{1}{p})-\beta} \|f\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.9}$$

for $0 < \beta \leq 1$ and $f \in L^q(\Omega)$.

Proof. For the proof of the first estimate, we refer to Proposition 3.1 in [28]. □

First we state the following lemma which will be useful in our main results (this lemma can be found in [29], Lemma 8, page 9).

Lemma 3.2. *see [27] Let $c > -1, d > -1$ such that $c + d \geq -1, h > 0$ and $t \in [0, T]$. For $h > 0$, the following limit holds*

$$\lim_{\gamma \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sup_{t \in [0, T]} t^h \int_0^1 r^c (1-r)^d e^{-\gamma t(1-r)} dr \right) = 0.$$

Theorem 3.3. *Let F satisfy the following condition*

$$\|F(\psi_1) - F(\psi_2)\|_{L^q(\Omega)} \leq K_f \|\psi_1 - \psi_2\|_{L^s(\Omega)}, \quad 1 \leq q \leq s. \tag{3.10}$$

where $1 \leq q \leq s$ and $\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s} < \frac{2}{N}$. Let us assume that $f \in L^q(\Omega)$ then Problem has a unique global existence in $\mathbf{Y}_{a,k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$ if k_0 enough large. Here a satisfies that

$$\frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s} \right) \leq a < 1. \tag{3.11}$$

In addition, the mild solution $z \in L^r(0, T; L^p(\Omega))$ and

$$\|z\|_{L^r(0, T; L^p(\Omega))} \leq C(p, q, r, m, T) T^{d - \frac{N}{4}(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{p})} \|f\|_{L^q(\Omega)} \tag{3.12}$$

for $1 < r < \frac{1}{d}$.

Proof. Let us define the space $\mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$ denotes the weighted space of all functions v , here $v \in \mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$ such that

$$\|w\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} := \sup_{t \in (0, T]} t^a e^{-kt} \|w(t, \cdot)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} < \infty,$$

where $s > 0$. We introduce the function Z as follows

$$Z\psi(t) = \mathcal{S}(t)\mathcal{Q}(t)u_0 + \int_0^t (t-r)\mathcal{S}(t-r)G(\psi(r))dr. \tag{3.13}$$

Let the zero function $\psi(t) = 0$. Then from the definition of two operators (3.3) and (3.4), it is obvious to see that

$$\begin{aligned} Z(\psi(t) = 0) &= \mathcal{S}(t)\mathcal{Q}(t)u_0 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-t\lambda_n} \left(\int_{\Omega} u_0(x)\varphi_n(x)dx \right) \varphi_n(x) \\ &\quad + t \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n e^{-t\lambda_n} \left(\int_{\Omega} u_0(x)\varphi_n(x)dx \right) \varphi_n(x). \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

We can rewrite the above expression as follows

$$Z(\psi(t) = 0) = e^{-t\Delta}u_0 + te^{-t\Delta}\Delta u_0. \tag{3.15}$$

With the help of Lemma (3.1), we derive that for $1 \leq q \leq s$

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z(\psi(t) = 0)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} &\leq \|e^{-t\Delta}u_0\|_{L^s(\Omega)} + \|te^{-t\Delta}\Delta u_0\|_{L^s(\Omega)} \\ &\leq C_1 t^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s})} \|u_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)} + tC_2 t^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}) - 1} \|u_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)} \\ &\leq C_3 t^{-\frac{N}{2}(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s})} \|u_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

Hence, we get

$$t^a e^{-kt} \|Z(\psi(t) = 0)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} \leq C_3 t^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \|u_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.17}$$

Noting that $a \geq \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)$, we deduce that $Z(\psi(t) = 0)$ belongs to the space $\mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$ for any $k > 0$. Take any two functions $\psi_1, \psi_2 \in \mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$. From (3.13) and Lemma (3.1), we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z\psi_1(t) - Z\psi_2(t)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} &\leq \int_0^t (t-r) \left\| \mathcal{S}(t-r) \left(G(\psi_1(r)) - G(\psi_2(r)) \right) \right\|_{L^s(\Omega)} dr \\ &\leq C_1 \int_0^t (t-r) (t-r)^{-\frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \left\| \left(G(\psi_1(r)) - G(\psi_2(r)) \right) \right\|_{L^q(\Omega)} dr. \end{aligned} \tag{3.18}$$

By global Lipschitz property of G , we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \|Z\psi_1(t) - Z\psi_2(t)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} &\leq C_1 K_f \int_0^t (t-r)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \left\| \psi_1(r) - \psi_2(r) \right\|_{L^s(\Omega)} dr \\ &= C_1 K_f \int_0^t (t-r)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} r^{-a} e^{kr} r^a e^{-kr} \left\| \psi_1(r) - \psi_2(r) \right\|_{L^s(\Omega)} dr \\ &\leq C_1 K_f \left(\int_0^t (t-r)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} r^{-a} e^{kr} dr \right) \left\| \psi_1 - \psi_2 \right\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))}. \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying both sides of the above equation by $t^a e^{-kt}$, we get the following estimate

$$\begin{aligned} t^a e^{-kt} \|Z\psi_1(t) - Z\psi_2(t)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} &\leq C_1 K_f t^a \left(\int_0^t (t-r)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} r^{-a} e^{k(r-t)} dr \right) \left\| \psi_1 - \psi_2 \right\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a,k}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.19}$$

Let us now to treat the term

$$L_k(t) = t^a \left(\int_0^t (t-r)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} r^{-a} e^{k(r-t)} dr \right).$$

By a change variable step $r = t\nu$, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} L_k(t) &= t^a \left(\int_0^1 (t-t\nu)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} (t\nu)^{-a} e^{k(t\nu-t)} t d\nu \right) \\ &= t^{2 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \int_0^1 (1-\nu)^{1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \nu^{-a} e^{-kt(1-\nu)} d\nu. \end{aligned} \tag{3.20}$$

Coming back to a closer look at the Lemma 3.2, we need to verify the condition

$$2 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right) > 0 \tag{3.21}$$

$$1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right) > -1, \quad -a > -1, \tag{3.21}$$

$$1 - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right) - a \geq -1. \tag{3.22}$$

It is obvious to see that (3.11) together with $\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s} < \frac{2}{N}$ leads to the above requirement. From these conditions combined with Lemma (3.2), we deduce that the following limit is correct

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{t \in [0, T]} L_k(t) = 0. \tag{3.23}$$

Hence, there exists a positive constant k_0 such that

$$\sup_{t \in [0, T]} L_{k_0}(t) \leq \frac{1}{2C_1 K_f}.$$

This inequality together with (3.19) allows us to deduce that

$$\|Z\psi_1 - Z\psi_2\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} \leq \frac{1}{2} \|\psi_1 - \psi_2\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))}. \tag{3.24}$$

Therefore, we derive that the mapping Z is a contraction mapping on

$$\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega)).$$

By applying Banach fixed point theorem, we deduce that Z has a fixed point $y \in \mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))$. It is obvious to see that y is a mild solution of Problem (1.1). Let us claim the well-posedness of the mild solution y . Since the fact that y is a fixed point of Z and in view of (3.17) and (3.24), we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \|y\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} &= \|Zy\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} \\ &\leq C_3 T^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \|y_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)} + \frac{1}{2} \|y\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

Therefore, we find that the following estimate

$$\|y\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} \leq 2C_3 T^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \|y_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.26}$$

The latter estimate lead immediately that

$$t^a e^{-k_0 t} \|y(\cdot, t)\|_{L^s(\Omega)} \leq \|y\|_{\mathbf{Y}_{a, k_0}((0, T]; L^s(\Omega))} \leq 2C_3 T^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \|y_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.27}$$

Therefore, multiply both sides of the above expression by $t^{-a} e^{k_0 t}$, we get

$$\|y(t, \cdot)\|_{L^p(\Omega)} \leq 2C_3 T^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} e^{k_0 T} t^{-a} \|y_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.28}$$

Since $1 < p < \frac{1}{a}$, we know that the proper integral $\int_0^T t^{-ap} dt < +\infty$. Hence, we follows from (3.28) that $y \in L^p(0, T; L^s(\Omega))$ and

$$\|y\|_{L^p(0, T; L^s(\Omega))} \lesssim T^{a - \frac{N}{2} \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{s}\right)} \|y_0\|_{L^q(\Omega)}. \tag{3.29}$$

The proof of our theorem is completed. □

4. Conclusion

In this work, we prove the global unique existence of the mild solution. Using the Banach’s fixed point theorem, and combination with the $L^p - L^q$ estimates. This paper seems to generalize previous results for the bi-parabolic equation in this direction.

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